

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 114

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 114

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 114:1 When Israel went forth ^afrom Egypt, The house of Jacob from a people of ^bstrange language, ² Judah became ^aHis sanctuary, Israel, ^bHis dominion.</p> <p>Psa. 114:3 The ^asea looked and fled; The ^bJordan turned back. ⁴ The mountains ^askipped like rams, The hills, like lambs. ⁵ What ^aails you, O sea, that you flee? O Jordan, that you turn back? ⁶ O mountains, that you skip like rams? O hills, like lambs?</p> <p>Psa. 114:7 ^aTremble, O earth, before the Lord, Before the God of Jacob, ⁸ Who ^aturned the rock into a ^bpool of water, The ^cflint into a fountain of water.</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">Psa. 114:1 בְּצֵאת יִשְׂרָאֵל מִמִּצְרַיִם בַּיַּת יִעֲקֹב מֵעַם לְעֹז: ² הַיְיִתָּה יְהוּדָה לְקֹדֶשׁוֹ יִשְׂרָאֵל מִמְּשֻׁלֹתָיו: ³ תִּיָּם רָאָה וַיִּנָּס הַיַּרְדֵּן יָפֹב לְאַחֲזֹר: ⁴ הַהָרִים רָקְדּוּ כְּאַיִלִים גְּבַעוֹת כַּבְּנֵי-צֹאן: ⁵ מִה־לֶּפֶן תִּיָּם כִּי תָנוּס הַיַּרְדֵּן תָּפֹב לְאַחֲזֹר: ⁶ הַהָרִים תְּרַקְדּוּ כְּאַיִלִים גְּבַעוֹת כַּבְּנֵי-צֹאן: ⁷ מִלְּפָנַי אֲדוֹן תְּוֹלֵי אֲרֶץ מִלְּפָנַי אֱלֹהֵי יִעֲקֹב: ⁸ תִּהְפְּכֵי הַצּוּר אֲגַם-מַיִם תִּלְמִישׁ לְמַעַיְנֹ-מַיִם:</p>

References

Psalm 114:1

^aEx 12:51; 13:3

^bPs 81:5

Psalm 114:2

^aEx 15:17; 29:45, 46; Ps 78:68, 69

^bEx 19:6

Psalm 114:3

^aEx 14:21; Ps 77:16

^bJosh 3:13, 16

Psalm 114:4

^aEx 19:18; Judg 5:5; Ps 18:7; 29:6; Hab 3:6

Psalm 114:5

^aHab 3:8

Psalm 114:7

^aPs 96:9

Psalm 114:8

^aEx 17:6; Num 20:11; Ps 78:15; 105:41

^bPs 107:35

^cDeut 8:15

Targum

Psa. 114:1 When Israel came out of Egypt, the house of Jacob from barbarian peoples – ² The company of the house of Judah became property of his Holy One, Israel of his rulers. ³ When the word of the LORD was revealed at the sea, the sea looked and retreated; the Jordan turned around. ⁴ When the Torah was given to his people, the mountains leapt like rams, the hills like offspring of the flock. ⁵ God said, “What is the matter, O sea, for you are retreating? O Jordan, that you are turning around?” ⁶ O mountains, leaping about like rams? O hills, like offspring of the flock? ⁷ In the presence of the lord, dance, O earth, in the presence of the God of Jacob. ⁸ Who turns the flint into a channel of water, the adamant to springs of water.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

This Psalm continues the praises of the LORD. Israel became noble when they left Egypt and had faith in the LORD when they were told to enter the Red Sea. The ultimate disciple of the people occurred at Sinai when they accepted the LORD's Torah and the burdens that it brings.

Verse two

The tribe of Yehudah (Judah) represented the concept of might and became the Sanctuary of God. This occurred when the Israelites left Egypt. Yehuda became God's own tribe and sacred to Him. This would explain why the Temple was built in Jerusalem, which was 90% in the tribe's territory.

Yehudah became His Sanctuary, Yisrael His spheres of dominion.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

MHK V5 1/17/2016

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

